

TO EXPLORE AND RECOGNIZE THE INFLUENCE AND PEDAGOGICAL PERSPECTIVE OF SINGAPORE'S SOCIAL POLICY ON CONTEMPORARY EDUCATION.

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Abstract: Many young people who want to study abroad dream of studying in one of the European countries. But there are not a few people who choose Asian countries to get quality education. In particular, educational institutions in Singapore, which are among the leaders in the world in terms of the level of education, have always attracted foreign students. Therefore, it is considered one of the most convenient countries not only to live a full, comfortable life, but also to get quality and affordable education.

Key words: education system, school students, Singapore, cluster, special, express, academic, higher education, result.

In recent years, the most modern science in higher educational institutions of the country and abroad directions and training of experts in the field of advanced technologies is a priority became one of the tasks. As a result of these measures, Singapore scientific and technical has become one of the world's leading countries in the field of development. At the moment this is it the country has a majority of scientists per 10,000 people (47) among the five countries. Singapore has its own level of spending on research and development in relation to GDP even ahead of its former colonial power Great Britain. In general, classroom instruction in Singapore is highly-scripted and uniform across all levels and subjects. Teaching is coherent, fit-for-purpose and pragmatic, drawing on a range of pedagogical traditions, both Eastern and Western. As such, teaching in Singapore primarily focuses on coverage of the curriculum, the transmission of factual and procedural knowledge, and preparing students for end-of-semester and national high stakes examinations. And because they do, teachers rely heavily on textbooks, worksheets, worked examples and lots of drill and practice. They also strongly emphasise mastery of specific procedures and the ability to represent problems clearly, especially in mathematics. Classroom talk is teacher-dominated and generally avoids extended discussion.

Classes are divided into groups of 4 people, each group is a unified team equipped with working materials: paper, notebook, pencil, etc. Teachers work in their workplaces and it is noisy around them. At the signal, the group changes rapidly, groups mix, and new groups (four or pairs) are formed. Given a question or a new task, children are actively sharing information and skills within a limited time. There are no boring students in such classes.

Intriguingly, Singaporean teachers only make limited use of “high leverage” or unusually effective teaching practices that contemporary educational research (at least in the West) regards as critical to the development of conceptual understanding and “learning how to learn”. For example, teachers only make limited use of checking a student’s prior knowledge or communicating learning goals and achievement standards. In addition, while teachers monitor student learning and provide feedback and learning support to students, they largely do so in ways that focus on whether or not students know the right answer, rather than on their level of understanding. In Singapore, the most gifted students can take the Integrated Program (IP). In this case, secondary school students in the country will be given the opportunity to take the A-level exam as soon as they complete 6 years of secondary education without having to pass the O-level exams. This opens the way for students to have more free time and study their chosen subjects more deeply. After finishing school, students can enter college. College graduates take the A-level certificate exam. Those who want to get technical education

continue their studies in 3-year polytechnics or 1-2-year technical education institutes. University education prepares students to enter higher education institutions. Singapore's higher education ranks among the leaders in the world. There are 5 institutes and 4 universities in the country, each of which guarantees high-level education. There are also 2 private universities and branches of several world-famous higher education institutions in the country.

Continuing higher education in Singapore is not as complicated as many people think. For this, it is necessary to have a deep knowledge of the English language. Also, foreign applicants who wish to study at one of Singapore's universities are required to provide a certificate or diploma of primary and secondary education, and an IELTS or TOEFL certificate confirming their knowledge of the English language. If there is no certificate, the applicant can study at one of the language schools in Singapore to get it. Singapore is also very generous in providing educational grants to students. Any talented student can apply for an educational scholarship or grant here. Scholarships are financed by the state, educational institutions or employers. The amount of payment allocated to students who get them fully covers the cost of education. Almost all higher education institutions in the country have their own scholarship program. Additional funds are often allocated to students of specialized courses. Some large enterprises and corporations prepare their future employees by paying the contract money of the specialists they are interested in. For this, an agreement is signed between the student and the company. According to him, after graduation, the student undertakes to work in that organization for several years. After all, it is natural that a student who graduated from one of the most prestigious universities in Singapore is interested in any organization as a qualified employee.

Many teachers are faced with the lack of interest in reading and creativity in modern students, and this is the most powerful tool in acquiring knowledge about the subject and developing skills in many ways. Teaching technology in Singapore's classrooms, including multiple forms and tools that empower and motivate anyone. creative, active students. The use of advanced educational structures makes it possible to revise the educational process and provide instructions for group and pair forms of working with students. The methods of the Singapore method are as follows: the team is divided into groups or pairs and studies a small part of the material itself. Each student regularly tries on the role of the teacher, explaining the essence of the question to his neighbor and in other words. And the teacher carries out "inclusive control": in turn, listening to one of the representatives of the microphone, he evaluates, corrects, helps and guides them.

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